

**Correlation Between Achievement in Chemistry in
Relation to Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students**

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Abstract

In this study, an attempt has been made to study the correlation between Achievement in Chemistry in relation to Notational Ability of Senior Secondary students. For Achievement in Chemistry, the Students' third term examination marks scored have been taken for this study and Notational Ability Test (NAT) Constructed and Validated by the Ramalingam Sivapathis and Manickavasagan. T (2022), were used to collect the data from a sample of 650 senior secondary students studying in Batticaloa District of Sri Lanka. The survey method had been followed and simple random sampling technique was used in administration of the research tools. The results of the analysis reveals that the level of Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability has been average. It is concluded that there is significant difference between male and female senior secondary students with respect to their Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability and that there is no significant difference between National and Provincial Senior Secondary Schools Students with respect to their Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability. The study also reveals that there is significant and positive relationship between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.

Key Words: *Achievement in Chemistry, Notational Ability, Gender, Type of School and Senior Secondary Students*

1. Introduction

Education plays a pivotal role in shaping the future of a nation, and within this domain, Science education is critical for fostering innovation and technological advancement. In Sri Lanka, secondary education includes a significant emphasis on subjects such as Chemistry, which is essential for students aspiring to careers in Science and Technology. Despite its importance, there is a noticeable gap in understanding the various factors that influence student Achievement in Chemistry within the Sri Lankan context. Addressing this gap is crucial for enhancing educational outcomes and developing targeted interventions.

Academic achievement is the important end-product of academic endeavors at all levels of education. The academic Achievement of Senior Secondary students includes their achievement in all subjects such as Languages, Science, Mathematics, Civics, etc.

Notation: the activity of representing something by a special system of marks or characters or symbol. Definitions of Chemical Notation a Notation used by Chemists to express technical facts in Chemistry Notation, Notational system a technical system of symbols used to represent special things.

2. Need and Importance of the Study

This study is significant as it provides a comprehensive analysis of factors affecting Student Achievement in Chemistry within the Sri Lankan context. The findings will be valuable for educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers in designing strategies to improve Chemistry education. By identifying key influences on student performance, the study aims to contribute to the enhancement of educational quality and student outcomes in secondary schools. Understanding these factors will enable the development of targeted interventions and policies that can effectively address the challenges faced in Chemistry education, thereby improving student achievement and fostering a stronger foundation in Science education for Sri Lankan students.

3. Review of Literature

Siri Sumedha Thero and Senevirathne (2024) investigated the influence of psychological and contextual factors on Chemistry Achievement among Senior Secondary school students in Sri Lanka. The research examines teachers' teaching styles, students' understanding of concepts, subject satisfaction, and attitudes toward Chemistry as psychological factors, with gender and school type as contextual characteristics. Using a sample of 302 students and 114 teachers from 13 schools in the Kegalle Education Zone. The results indicate that attitude towards chemistry and gender significantly influence student achievement. All variables except school location have a positive effect on student achievement.

Nandhini and Jayanthi (2022) conducted a study on relationship between academic achievement in chemistry and family environment of higher secondary school students, were used to collect the data from a sample of 600 higher secondary school students studying in Cuddalore District of Tamilnadu State in India. It is concluded that the average level of academic achievement in chemistry and family environment of higher secondary school students, there is significant difference in the gender and type of management of higher secondary school students with respect to their academic achievement in chemistry and family

environment, there is significant and positive relationship between academic achievement in chemistry and family environment of higher secondary school students.

Manickavasagan (2019) conducted with the aim of finding out the level of Achievement in Chemistry and their Reasoning Ability of higher secondary students in Perambalur District of Tamilnadu. From the systematic analysis the investigator has arrived in results that the Achievement in Chemistry is average and Reasoning Ability of the entire sample is high. Further a significant difference found between the boys and girls of higher secondary school with respect to their Reasoning Ability. A positive relationship is also found between the Achievement in Chemistry and their Reasoning Ability. Based on the results obtained through this study the suitable recommendations also were made by the investigator to improve the Achievement and their Reasoning Ability.

4. Operational Definitions of the Study

Achievement in Chemistry

The present study deals with the Achievement in Chemistry subject of the Senior Secondary Students. Here, the Achievement in Chemistry refers to the third term examination marks scored by the 12th grade senior secondary students.

Notational Ability

Notational ability refers to the ability of working with symbols and numbers. In the present study Notational ability refers to an ability which includes symbols and number sequence in Chemistry.

5. Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the level of the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students.
2. To find out the level of the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their gender.
4. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their type of school.
5. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their gender.
6. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their type of school.
7. To find out whether there is any significant relationship between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.

6. Hypotheses of the Study

1. The level of the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students is low.
2. The level of the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students is low.
3. There is no significant difference in the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their gender.
4. There is no significant difference in the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their type of school.
5. There is no significant difference in the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their gender.
6. There is no significant difference in the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their type of school.
7. There is no significant relationship between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.

7. Method of the Study and Sample Used

The normative survey method was adopted in the present study. In order to collect the required data, Achievement in Chemistry the Students' third term examination marks scored by the 12th grade and Notational Ability Test (NAT) constructed and validated by the Ramalingam Sivapathis and Manickavasagan. T (2022). Simple random sampling technique has been employed to collect the data from 650 senior secondary students studying in Batticaloa District of Sri Lanka.

8. Analysis of Data and Interpretation

The data collected were descriptively analyzed by employing the following statistical techniques:

1. Descriptive Analyses (Mean and Standard Deviation)
2. Differential Analyses ('t' test and 'F' test) and
3. Correlation Analyses ('r' value)

Descriptive Analysis

Result of Hypothesis 1

The level of the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students is low.

Table – 1: Showing the Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Achievement in Chemistry

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Achievement in Chemistry	650	50.35	17.79

From the above table-1 the calculated mean and standard deviation for Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students of entire sample is found to be 50.35 and 17.79 respectively. The mean score lay in between (34-67). Hence, the framed hypothesis 1 is rejected and it is concluded that the level of Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students is average.

Result of Hypothesis 2

The level of the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students is low.

Table – 2: Showing the Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Notational Ability

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Notational Ability	650	22.85	8.13

From the above table-2 the calculated mean and standard deviation for Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students of entire sample is found to be 22.85 and 8.13 respectively. The mean score lay in between (21-32). Hence, the framed hypothesis 2 is rejected and it is concluded that the level of Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students is average.

Differential Analysis

Result of Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their gender.

Table-3

‘t’ test for Achievement in Chemistry scores of Senior Secondary Students with regard to Gender

Sub-sample	Sub-Category	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	295	47.04	18.66	3.01	Significant
	Female	355	55.66	16.21		

From the above table-3, With regard to Gender, the calculated ‘t’ value is found to be 3.01; which is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the framed hypothesis 3 is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significant difference between male and female Senior Secondary Students with respect to their Achievement in Chemistry. It is also inferred that female students are more Achievement in Chemistry than the male students.

Result of Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their type of school.

Table-4

‘t’ test for Achievement in Chemistry scores of Senior Secondary Students with regard to Type of School

Sub-sample	Sub-Category	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Significance at 0.05 level
Type of School	National	274	51.76	17.77	1.37	Not Significant
	Provincial	376	53.23	17.16		

From the above table-4, With regard to Type of School, the calculated ‘t’ value is found to be 1.37; which is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the framed hypothesis 4 is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between national and provincial Senior Secondary Students in their Achievement in Chemistry.

Result of Hypothesis 5

There is no significant difference in the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their gender.

Table-5

‘t’ test for Notational Ability scores of Senior Secondary Students with regard to Gender

Sub-sample	Sub-Category	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	295	21.58	8.60	3.77	Significant
	Female	355	25.64	7.83		

From the above table-5, With regard to Gender, the calculated ‘t’ value is found to be 3.77; which is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the framed hypothesis 5 is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significant difference between male and female Senior Secondary Students with respect to their Notational Ability. It is also inferred that female students are more Notational Ability than the male students.

Result of Hypothesis 6

There is no significant difference in the Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students with respect to their type of school.

Table-6

‘t’ test for Notational Ability scores of Senior Secondary Students with regard to Type of School

Sub-sample	Sub-Category	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Level of Significance at 0.05 level
Type of School	National	274	21.95	8.58	1.25	Not Significant
	Provincial	376	22.53	8.05		

From the above table-6, With regard to Type of School, the calculated ‘t’ value is found to be 1.25; which is lesser than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the framed hypothesis 6 is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between national and provincial Senior Secondary Students in their Notational Ability.

Correlation Analysis

Result of Hypothesis 7

There is no significant relationship between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.

Table-7: Showing the Correlation values between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students

Variables	N	‘r’ value	Level of Significance
Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability	650	0.430**	Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table-7 shows that, the co-efficient of correlation between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students is found to be significant [$r=0.430$ at 0.01 level]. Therefore hypothesis 7 is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant and positive relationship between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.

9. Findings of the Study

- The level of Achievement in Chemistry of Senior Secondary Students is average.
- The level of Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students is average.
- There is a significant difference between male and female Senior Secondary Students with respect to their Achievement in Chemistry.

- There is no significant difference between national and provincial Senior Secondary Students in their Achievement in Chemistry.
- There is a significant difference between male and female Senior Secondary Students with respect to their Notational Ability.
- There is no significant difference between national and provincial Senior Secondary Students in their Notational Ability.
- There is significant and positive relationship between Achievement in Chemistry and Notational Ability of Senior Secondary Students.

10. Recommendations

1. The senior secondary school teachers and the government should provide harmonious environment in the schools for better achievement in Chemistry.
2. The government should provide organized laboratory facilities in the schools for better Achievement in Chemistry.
3. The school teachers should facilitate the practical mentioned in tier Chemistry syllabus to acquire related skills of senior secondary students to enhance the Achievement in Chemistry.
4. Effective methods of teaching like e-learning, video conferencing and conferences may promote Achievement in Chemistry among Senior Secondary Students.
5. The finding of the present study reveals that the students have positive correlation between achievement score and their Notational Ability. It reveals that the Notational Ability and their achievement scores are in same position. So, if one want improves their Notational Ability or Achievement in Chemistry that individual must develop skills in both of them.

11. Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing student achievement in chemistry in Sri Lankan senior secondary schools. The results highlight the significant roles of psychological factor such as notational ability, as well as contextual characteristics like gender and school type. The findings suggest that enhancing teacher training, fostering positive student attitudes, and ensuring relevant and engaging curriculum practices can improve student outcomes in chemistry.

12. References

1. Agarwal, Y.P. (1986). Statistical Methods Concepts, Application and Computation, Delhi: Sterling Publishers.

2. Allen L. Edwards (1956). *Statistical methods for the behavioral sciences*, New York : Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
3. Allen L. Edwards (1960). *Statistical analysis*, New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston.
4. Guilford, J.P. (1939). *General psychology*. New York, NY: D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc.
5. Henry E, Garret, (2008), *Statistics in Psychology and Education*”, Surjeet Publishing House, Delhi.
6. Kundu, C.L. & Tutoo, D.N. (1991), *Educational Psychology*, Sterling Publishers Private Limited, New Delhi.
7. Manickavasagan (2019). Higher secondary students' Achievement in chemistry in relation to their reasoning ability. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, 6(5), 238-243.
8. Nandhini & Jayanthi (2022). Relationship Between Academic Achievement in Chemistry and Family Environment of Higher Secondary School students. *International Journal of Research*, 9(3), 179-187.
9. Siri Sumedha Thero & Senevirathne (2024). The Impact of Psychological and Contextual Factors on Student Achievement in Chemistry: A Quantitative Study in Sri Lankan Senior Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 9(8), DOI : <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/IJISRT24AUG113>.